

Metal Ion-Nalidixic Acid Antibiotic Interaction : Formation Constants, Molecular Modelling and pH Metric Studies

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The quinolones or more correctly the fluorinated piperazine quinolones are analogous to the drug nalidixic acid¹. Nalidixic acid (HNaI) inhibits the replication of DNA² by inhibition of the DNA-gyrase. The later is probably a metalloenzyme³ and by interaction with the DNA molecule by an intermediate (iron complex)⁴ that acts as a carrier of nalidixic acid. It has been reported⁵ that quinolone antibacterial agents do not bind to gyrase subunit but rather to DNA and the mechanism of action is based on drug-DNA complex formation.

HNaI acts as a bidentate chelating agent^{6,7}. In order to enhance understanding of drug-metal ion interaction, it is important to assess the interaction of HNaI with metal ions present in the biological systems. Here pH-metric titrations have been carried to estimate the formation constants of the species formed. Molecular modelling study has been conducted to find out the active metal species involved.

Results and Discussion

Titration data for Co-nalidixic acid complex are given in Table 1. The overall equilibrium constants for the complexes are given in Table 2.

The order of magnitude of the stability constants of divalent metal complexes (1:1) of nalidixic acid is Mn^{II}

TABLE 1—TITRATION DATA FOR CO-NALIDIXIC ACID COMPLEX

TMAH ml	pH	TMAH ml	pH	TMAH ml	pH
0.0	4.03	1.5	8.05	3.0	11.37
0.1	4.08	1.6	8.33	3.1	11.57
0.2	4.16	1.7	8.55	3.2	11.75
0.3	4.25	1.8	8.70	3.3	11.93
0.4	4.37	1.9	8.84	3.4	12.58
0.5	4.52	2.0	8.97	3.5	13.02
0.6	4.77	2.1	9.10	3.6	13.27
0.7	5.26	2.2	9.22	3.7	13.33
0.8	5.72	2.3	9.36	3.8	13.38
0.9	6.15	2.4	9.50	3.9	13.41
1.0	6.41	2.5	9.66	4.0	13.44
1.1	6.63	2.69	9.85	4.1	13.48
1.2	6.92	2.7	10.11	4.2	13.50
1.3	7.30	2.8	10.52	4.3	13.52
1.4	7.70	2.9	10.98		

$\sigma_{fit} = 0.01440$.

TABLE 2—OVERALL EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS FOR METAL-NALIDIXIC ACID COMPLEX

Metal ion	$\log \beta_{HL}$	$\log \beta_{ML}$	σ_{fit}
Co	9.2460	4.6500	0.014400
Fe	9.2460	4.4600	0.004693
Zn	9.2460	5.4317	0.047357
Mn	9.2460	4.1389	0.069473

$\beta_{HL} = [HL]/[L][H]$, $\beta_{ML} = [ML]/[M][L]$.

$< Fe^{II} < Co^{II} < Zn^{II}$. The order can be accounted for by the decrease in metal ion radius from Mn to Zn and by the crystal field stabilisation energy increasing from Fe to Cu. The order is mainly valid if the donor atom nitrogen or oxygen is present in the ligand. Nalidixic acid forms stable complexes with Fe, Co and Zn⁸. Metal ions are found to be necessary for the stabilisation and function of DNA⁹. Nalidixic acid forms stable complexes with metal ions of bacterial DNA and destabilises the active structure of DNA by this strong binding. This has been confirmed by the fact that under the effect of nalidixic acid DNA loses its supercoiling and cell elongation occurs, resulting in cell death¹⁰. The higher stability of iron complex supports the hypothesis that the mode of action of nalidixic acid as a drug is through a iron carrier⁷.

Molecular modelling studies : Molecular mechanics is a nonquantum mechanical method of obtaining optimum structures. Force field calculations are a standard way to obtain a great deal of information like structure and energy of molecules rather quickly and easily¹¹. In our experiment, molecular mechanics, force field MM2 developed by Allinger¹⁵ has been used to determine the minimization energy. Molecular mechanics is easier to understand than the quantum mechanical methods. The forces can be described by potential energy functions of structural features like bond lengths, bond angles, non-bonded interactions and so on. The combination of these potential energy functions is the force field. Molecular modelling software based on MM2 force field has the ability to handle transition metals. Energy minimization was repeated several times to find the global minimum. We found that the MM2 energy for iron complex (27.42 kcal) is lower than nalidixic acid (41.47 kcal). This confirms the strong complexation behaviour of nalidixic acid with trace metal ions,

which is also supported by formation constants and species distribution curves (Fig. 1). Again from molecular mechanics it is confirmed that the chelation occurs through the 4-keto group and 5-carboxylate group of nalidixic acid. This model is consistent with the invariant nature of the 4-

Fig. 1. Species distribution curves for nalidixic acid and its Co^{II} complexes.

keto group in the closely related antibacterial quinolones. Again this was supported by Mendoza-Diaz *et al.*¹² by X-ray crystallography that the 4-keto group of nalidixic acid is involved in the complexation of quinolones with Cu^{II} -phenanthroline¹³.

Experimental

The purity of nalidixic acid (Fluka) was checked by tlc and m.p. All other chemicals were of analytical grade.

The pH-metric method was used for the determinations of pK_a value of the ligand and metal stability constants using a Radiometer PHM83 instrument with a combined glass electrode. The equilibration of glass electrode in 75% DMSO was carried out by the reported procedure¹⁴. To ensure constant ionic strength (0.1 M) during the titrations, NaClO_4 (Fluka) was used in requisite amounts. A solution (0.026 M) of tetramethylammonium hydroxide (TMAH) (E. Merck) in 75% DMSO-water was used as the titrant which was standardised with oxalic acid. The titrations were performed under a stream of presaturated nitrogen. All measurements were made in 75% DMSO-water medium

at $25^\circ (\pm 0.5^\circ)$. Solution concentrations of the ligand in the presence and absence of the metal ions were in the order of 5×10^{-3} M. Stepwise protonation constants within range of the potentiometric titrations (upto pH 12.0) were calculated by fitting the pH data with the help of the program PKAS. Formation constants of the complexes were determined by direct potentiometric titration using the program BEST¹⁴. A PC/AT computer was used for computing the results.

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